

THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS ON MOBILE LEGEND ADDICTION IN BARANGAY TINAJEROS, MALABON CITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15166978>

ABSTRACT

Online game addiction such as playing Mobile Legend is prevalent among teenagers nowadays. Studies have shown that playing Mobile Legend has positive and negative effects on its players depending on the number of hours and severity of addiction. This phenomenological study aimed to determine the causes and effects of playing Mobile Legend among Senior High School students in Barangay Tinajeros, Malabon City. It employed a purposive sampling technique and semi-structured interview, where nineteen (19) individuals participated in the study. The respondents consisted of twelve (12) Senior High School students, five (5) parents, and two (2) teachers at Acacia National High School. The study showed that majority of the respondents suffered from stomachache, dizziness, eyestrain, incompetence, laziness, procrastination, and other negative behaviors such as stress. and fatigue. On the other hand, majority of the students were able to hurdle their academic difficulties and fulfill their responsibilities at home. In totality, playing Mobile Legend does not affect the responsibility and academic performance of the participants. This simply implied that the participants can effectively manage their time, and they know how to prioritize their studies and responsibilities at home.

Keywords: *Mobile Legend addiction, online video games, electronic games, Senior High School students*

INTRODUCTION

The modern world is surrounded by advancements and modern technologies that bring comfort and convenience to the lives of many individuals. In the study of Haleem, et.al, (2022), they claimed that technology has emerged as a tool to achieved sustainable development of the United Nations. The use of technology in various fields ensure that human civilization will continue to grow and will find ways on how to enhance the world we live in. However, there are also contentions that technology may bring threats to human beings and even our society. Take for instance, the study of Sorokoumova, et. al. (2021) stated that the digital addiction of the students which can be attributed from one of the by-products of modern technology may lead them to pay less attention in their studies. Legg (2024) posited that the overuse of mobile devices and getting immersed in technology, particularly social media, may result to isolation, depression and anxiety, eyestrain, poor posture, sleep problems, reduced physical activity, lack of attention, low academic performance, delays in social and emotional development, delays in language development, or even aggressive behaviors. In the study of Costanza, C, Vetri, L et. al. (2023) concurred that gaming addiction, otherwise known as gaming disorder, has adverse impacts on social, psychological, physical and financial problems. With the emergence of modern technology, many teenagers are obsessed in playing online video games, particularly Mobile Legends. Hence, this study emphasized how online game influences the Senior High School students in Barangay Tinajeros, Malabon City.

Online games, also known as electronic games or online video games that are played in the computers using Internet, is a multibillion-dollar business (Ray, 2025). A trusted source of market data and statistics based in Dublin, Ireland, named Research and Markets recently published that the exponential growth and fame of online games emerged due to widespread use of smartphones, high-speed internet, and cloud gaming. As a result, it was estimated that there are about 3.32 billion players worldwide, where Asia dominated the market with around 1.5 billion players. Historically, the popularity of electronic games can be traced in the early days of 1970s, but it grew in 1990s with the rapid accessibility of the Internet. The massive multiplayer online game (MMOG) in 2007 to 2010 generated millions of subscribers. In 2016, Moontoon, developed and published a mobile multiplayer online battle arena (MOBA) which is now known as Mobile Legends: Big Bang (ML or MLBB). Ike, et.al. (2021) posited that Southeast Asia dominated the market niche of the Mobile Legend, where it garnered almost fifty-six (56) percent of its total revenue.

Playing online games, particularly Mobile Legend, is a prominent pastime activity among younger generation. Their utilization and consumption is not based on what they need but what they want. Edombingo, et.al. (2024) stated that in 2021 the Philippines placed second spot in terms of Mobile Legend downloads, with an impressive 41.2 installs. A plethora of studies have shown that playing Mobile Legend has both positive and adverse effects among its players. Kharade (2022) and Crucianu, et. al. (2024) provided warned the Mobile Legend players on its harmful effects such as physical, and mental issues. On the other hand, Kenskin and Aral (2022) emphasized that although playing Mobile Legend may provided physical problems, it may also help the young individuals to improve their reflexes and language development. Haidar (2022) and Edombingo, et.al. (2024)

emphasized that playing Mobile Legend is not detrimental to the academic success of the players provided that restrictions and time limits will be imposed on them.

Research Questions

The main purpose of this study was to determine the causes and effects of Mobile Legend addiction in the lives of Senior High School students in Barangay Tinajeros, Malabon City. Further, it aimed to find the actions that must be taken in order to assist the students who are hooked up in playing Mobile Legend.

Specifically, the study aims to seek answer to the following research questions:

1. How does online gaming addiction occur?
2. What are the effects of online gaming addiction to:
 - 2.1. Physical Health
 - 2.2. Mental Health
 - 2.3. Responsibilities
 - 2.4. School Performance

METHODOLOGY

This phenomenological study was conducted at Barangay Tinajeros, Malabon City to gather information on the experiences of the Senior High School students who are hooked up in playing Mobile Legend. Alhazmi and Kaufmann (2022) posited that phenomenology allows researchers to describe and understand human social experiences by considering the three core aspects of the study such as: aims of the study; philosophical assumptions on the knowledge sought to be addressed; and investigative strategies.

Using purposive sampling technique, a total of nineteen (19) individuals voluntarily and willingly participated in the study. The respondents consisted of twelve (12) Senior High School students, five (5) parents, and two (2) teachers at Acacia National High School. Campbell (2020) posited that purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling that where the researcher intentionally chose the respondents based on their distinct characteristics, experiences, and beliefs. Semi-structured interview was used where the researcher prepared some questions but also made follow up questions to further clarify the answers of the respondents.

Prior to the interview, all participants were contacted and informed of the topic and possible questions that will be asked. They were informed of the actual date of home visit and interview. They were also informed that the names and personal identities will not be disclosed for data protection and privacy. Likewise, the purpose of the home visit and interview was discussed ahead of time to gain their trust and confidence from the researcher.

During the interview, the researcher reiterated that the consent of the respondents is necessary, and they may withdraw anytime they wish to. It was clarified that voice recording through mobile phone will be facilitated and all recorded information will be treated with utmost confidentiality. It was also mentioned that no personal judgment will be provided and questions to be asked were not offensive and violative to the rights and emotions of the participants.

The recorded conversations with the respondents in Filipino dialect were retrieved and reviewed. While listening to the recorded conversations, the researcher indexed labels to words and phrases based on the responses of the participants. Through coding, the themes and concepts were identified and organized. Aside from thematic analysis, where extracted data were classified into themes, content analysis was also used for deeper insights and contexts.

RESULTS

Occurrence of online gaming addiction - Complacency

Some psychological studies have found that spending more time on the Internet reduces a person's ability to communicate effectively with friends, peers, and family members, especially parents. According to studies, the human brain is easily damaged, and one of the reasons is the use of technology. The researchers discovered that senior high school students tend to play online games without knowing the risks and dangers. Adolescents' mobile game addiction is associated with social anxiety, anxiety, and depression. It has been found that smartphone game addiction is associated with social anxiety, hopelessness, and depression. A deeper look at gender differences in the paths from mobile game addiction to mental health consequences was conducted, and the results found out that teenage boys who play mobile games are more addicted, which reports higher levels of social anxiety. Limitations and implications for mental health training were also highlighted. Online games are harming the quality of time spent fulfilling their household chores and other responsibilities. For example, Student A stated that his addiction to online gaming has adversely affected his daily life even as well as his studies. And on the other hand, Student B response was:

“Schedule, routine, time management at goal. Inaalam ko muna yung mga responsibilidad ko na nakatakda at dapat tapusin na gawain sa araw na iyon. Nililista ko at tinatapos hanggat maaari sa tamang oras at kapag natapos na tsaka ako maglalaro sa aking libreng oras.”

Based on the respondents' responses, online game addiction can manifest itself as incompetence, laziness, procrastination, and other negative behavior. The study found that playing online games had no negative impact on students' scores. It is also intended here that it also depends on how they manage their time. People cope with their emotional distress by playing online games, but excessive use of online games over a long period of time can separate individuals from real-life relationships, thus causing more severe

mental health problems, such as depression. Based on the study, it clearly verifies the study of Wang, J., et. al. (2019) that one of the main causes of several health problems is that adolescents most likely play online games for satisfaction oblivious to its risks. It is also said that fans of any particularly interesting recreational activity, such as online games and not limited to gaming, spend a lot of time thinking and discussing their individual leisure activities.

Manifestations of Online Game Addiction — Physical Health

The researchers of the study investigated the manifestations of online game addiction in terms of physical health. Most of the Respondents of the study said that playing Mobile Legends affect their physical health. To give an instance, Student A said that he's getting thinner, while Student B said that it causes him a loss of sleep and loss of activeness when it comes to communicating, and Student C said that it playing Mobile Legends could affect the physical health when skipping meals. On the other hand, Student D said that:

“Oo, dahil kung minsan ay sumasakit ang aking tiyan at kung minsan ay nahihilo lalo na kung masyadong nakababad ang mata ko sa paglalaro.”

Manifestations of Online Game Addiction — Mental Health

Many said that online gaming helps a person's mental health, it helps to relieve stress from loneliness and boredom which a student usually feels. But the results of the survey conducted for this study show the opposite of the said statement. Addiction to online games also has a detrimental effect on a person's mental health. The negative impact is extremely distressing for a student. Most of the subjects of the study have responded that playing online games is not helping their mental health. But according to student A, playing online games helps his/her mental health. He/She momentarily forgets his/her problems because his/her attention is focused on the game. Whereas student B said that: “When I experiencing many defeats I'm getting more stress than being relieved from stress.”

Manifestations of Online Game Addiction — Responsibilities

The researcher of the study conducted an investigation on the manifestations of online gaming addiction in terms of responsibilities. A significant number of the respondents of the study stated that their priority is to finish their household chores before playing mobile legends. In particular, respondent A stated that having time management helps you to equally allocate time for responsibilities, while respondent B said that he's doing his priorities before engaging in any leisure activities, and student C stated that he's doing his duties in their house including his school works before playing mobile legends. However, respondent D said that:

“Tumutulong ako sa mga gawain minsan. Kapag wala namang gagawin, nakikipaglaro ako sa mga pamangkin ko gano'n. Mas nakikita ko kasi yung sistema ng mundo ngayon kesa sa lagi lang akong naglalaro, nakahiga nakakatamad din tsaka nakakapagod.”

Manifestations of Online Game Addiction — School Performance

Addiction to online games can also affect a student's daily life. Once a person plays online games it gives life to him/her into the new world cause for him/her to forget the real world. Addiction, lack of control, and self-restraint in playing can consume a lot of time causing a student to forget his or her tasks as a student. Most of the respondents of this study indicated that online gaming addiction has a detrimental effect and interferes with their school performances. Identical to student A, his/her focus is lost when studying or doing his/her school tasks, his/her eyes dimmed and he/she's always daydreaming about the game during His/her classes. Whereas student B said that:

“Noon, bumaba lahat ng grades ko. Napabaya ko, talagang nakita ko na ang panget sobra ng grade ko. Makakita man ako ng line of 8 sa card, parang wala lang kasi alam ko sa sarili na di rin ako natuto, wala akong natutunan, at wala akong effort na ginawa. So, hindi ko pa rin deserved yung ganoong grade.”

DISCUSSION

Existence of Mobile Legends

Online game addiction such Mobile Legend is prevalent among teenagers, particularly the Senior High School students. The term addiction is a prolonged and exaggerated behavior that causes physical and psychological issues. Based on the results of the study, it was found that majority of the respondents are hooked up in playing Mobile Legend as part of their recreational activity and a way to cope with their emotional distress. This result concurred with the study of Imayani and Anas (2020), where they stated that the factors that cause the addiction to Mobile Legend are: (1). Existence of rewards and prizes; (2). Reduction of boredom and loneliness; (3). Low level of socialization; (4). Low self-esteem and self-efficacy; and (5). Sense of enthusiasm and excitement when playing.

Effects of Mobile Legend

Based on the answers of the respondents, it can be gleaned that Mobile Legend adversely affects the physical and school performance of the students. Albeit, the study of Adhyatman (2024) discussed the implications of Mobile Legend on the physical health of the students such as problems on eyesight, headaches, and typhoid fevers. This study includes another physical health issue that can be derived from playing such as stomach-ache. In terms of school performance, it contradicted the study of Edombingo, et. al. (2024) where it reported that there is no significant relationship between playing Mobile Legend and academic performance. The study of Gabrito, et. al. (2023) concluded that the effects of Mobile Legend to the academic performance of the respondents depends on how the students manage their time in playing the said game.

On the other hand, responsibility and mental health of the respondents are not affected by the playing Mobile Legend. It is similar to the result of the study of Mahinay, et. al (2024) where they discussed that playing Mobile Legend inculcates the values of

optimism, sportsmanship, resilience, and recognition of failures and defeats. Adhyatman (2024) posited that playing Mobile Legend enhances problem solving skills, boosts motivation and socialization.

Conclusions

In light of the aforementioned results and findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Majority of the respondents are hooked up in playing Mobile Legend to relieve emotional distress and consider it as a form of recreational activity.
2. Mobile Legends: Bang Bang, sometimes known as ML or MLBB, is a mobile multiplayer online battle arena (MOBA) game developed by Moonton. It has adverse effects on the physical health and mental health of the Senior High School students.
3. Playing Mobile Legend does not significantly affect the responsibilities and academic performance of the participants, where it can be inferred that the students who participated in the study know how to manage their time and how to prioritize their chores and responsibilities at home.

Recommendations

Based on the results, findings, and conclusion of this study, the researcher highly recommended that future research with similar objectives must highlight the following points:

1. Further examine the adverse effect of online gaming addiction on the emotional health and the social life of an individual. As much as possible, utilize an instrument that quantitatively assess the level of complexity of Mobile Legend addiction among the respondents.
2. Engage and educate the stakeholders of the society such as the parents, learning community, local government units, and medical professionals to determine the causes and effects of Mobile Legend addiction among the students.
3. Future researchers are encouraged to conduct further study the causes and effects of Mobile Legend addiction among the students and draft action plans on how to effectively resolve the same.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

All processes and methodologies employed in this study complied with applicable laws and regulations that exist in the Philippines. The consent and voluntariness of the respondents to participate in the study were taken into consideration prior data were gathered. This study adhered with the ethical norms, transparency, trust and integrity of research.

Acknowledgments

The proponent of the study extends his sincere appreciation to all the individuals who helped him in this study. First, the participants of the study who voluntarily participated and answered all the queries of the researcher. Their insights provided information that serve as highlights of the study. Second, National University, Philippines, an institution that promotes the spirit and culture of research among their faculty members. Third, the teachers at Acacia National High School, who unselfishly provided their experiences, beliefs and insights to selected students of Senior High School.

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